

8T – Spin Chronicles

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series (derived in March 2021) in spin representation, the author will attempt to reason the particle wave duality but from a different angle. The Bosons are on the prime critical line, which is one-half. And thus can have Fermion spin, but the invariant three prevents it and making it spin one, from the second coupling and above. The analysis also includes

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the idea of spin. As one can see, each Boson is firstly described by spin, which is not an integer, i.e. one half. That is an indication to it's particle like traits which are preserved. Than since each coupling term is containing an additional term on the prime critical line, which is the invariant three, the spin total reaches to one. Since the invariant three is always there, the minimal spin which Bosons from the second coupling term and above will have is one. Since the Higgs does not have this invariant three which is the sole generator of net variations as we now believe, it is represented by spin zero. Than if an additional photon is getting scattered onto the photon emitted the spin of the system than again varies, which is presented in the 8T thesis:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = \left[2N_2 + \frac{3}{2}\right]$$

The 8T emphasized the spin variation by half unit as a result of measurement, changing the photon from wave like to a particle like, at first used in the context of super symmetry. Such a view of analysis than indicate that the super-partners are not needed. That is because the same particle represents spectra of behaviors according to spin variations. It is the same particle. Later view of SUSY showed that using the SEW unification it is a possible to predict a morphism from the photon onto the electron, as it is isomorphic to the W boson of the weak interaction, same as for the Gluon. Therefore, at high energies Bosons can turn into matter, without any need for super partners. Additional important point, which were not mentioned before. First, since each photon contain energy of certain amount, it is impossible to measure with it without interfering with the experiment. That is the analog of QM principle of uncertainty with regards to time an energy. Even a measurement with a Higgs will interfere with the system as the Higgs contains quanta of energy given it has a positive mass. Although the Higgs will not interfere with the spin, it will interfere with the environment of the experiment, making the energy of the system larger than before.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma + H^0 \rightarrow 2N_2 + 1$$

$$H^0 \Leftrightarrow E_n$$

$$E_n > 0$$

So despite the Higgs does not affect the system at the spin level, it does vary the energy. The invariance of total spin due to the Higgs can be put using an automorphism of the coupling term:

$$H^0: 2N_2 + 1 \rightarrow 2N_2 + 1$$

The second important point is the following, at the heart of it all, each Boson (weak and above) start with spin one-half. Than due to additional element it receives total spin one. It is possible to classify the behavior of Bosons according to the number of elements in the coupling term. Odd number of elements in the coupling term would lead to a behavior of a particle, while even number would lead to an integer spin, a wave like behavior; we take into account the invariant three and the outer Bosons, manifested as prime outside the bracket. Define the summation of elements on the prime critical line:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \mathcal{P}_i = \mathcal{S}$$

$$2 \mid N \rightarrow True$$

Than wavelike:

$$\mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{B}$$

Else, it would be particle like

$$2 \mid N \rightarrow False$$

$$\mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathfrak{P}$$

Since the lepton is represented as the invariant three, which is also the element used to describe the Boson of the weak interaction, which could either behave like a particle or a wave, depends upon the total elements on the critical line, so does the electron. That is given by the previously mentioned equivalence relation:

$$W^- \equiv (e^-) \tag{1.61}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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